

A UNIQUE INSCRIPTION OF SULTAN
HOSHANG SHAH GHORI FROM KAMPAL

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In January 1991, I came to know about the existence of a Persian Inscription in an old building which is called Ahilya Bai's **Kachaheri** (Court), at village Kampal in Indore District of Madhya Pradesh, India. This important record constitutes the first inscription of Hoshang Shah, son and successor of Dilawar Khan, the Founder of independent Sultnate of Malwa in 1401 A.D.

The inscription is fixed on a wall of an inner chamber, above the arch in an old house, which, from outside, appears to be a residential building. It bears a five-line text in Persian, executed in **Naskh** script of a fairly high order, which reminds us the calligraphical excellence of the inscriptions of the later Tughlugs and of the Sultans of Gujarat. The inscription states that in 817 A.H. (1414 A.D.), during the reign of Hasamud-Dunya wad-Din Azam Humayun Alp Khan, a mosque was constructed by Hazarat-i-Subbani Abul'l-Hamid Alp Khani on 15th day of Jamada II 817 A.H.

The importance of the inscription lies in the fact that for the first time, in inscription, the full titles of King, similar to that as found on his coins had been engraved! the absence of King's name Hoshang Shah, makes the inscription significant, revealing that by this time Alp Khan did not assume the name Hoshang Shah.

The study of numismatic data of this ruler does not help in revealing that when did Alp Khan assumed the title of Hoshang Shah. Formost of his earlier copper coins are without date.

A tentative English rendering of the Persian Text on he inscription reveals that during the reign of Alexander Exhalted, equal to the dignity of Faridun (a King in Persia), Husamud-Dunya wa'd-Din Azam Humayun, Alp Khan, may God brighten his abode. The Foundation of the mosque

1. For titles on his silver coins refer to, **The Journal of Numismatic Society of Madhya Pradesh** Vol.II, pp.

was completed, by Abul'al-Haleem, this humble and hopeful servant of the King (Alp Khan's) on Fifteenth of Jamada II, year (A.H.) Seventeen and eight hundred (15th Jamada II A.H. 817).

A comparative study of the Calligraphy of this inscription with that of 817 A.H.² (24th Rajab = 9th Oct. 1414 A.D.) once housed in Dharamshala and now deposited in the Archaeological Museum at Mandu, reveals that it was engraved by the same calligraphist who had engraved above mentioned inscription.

This is the first and the last inscription so far known, from the territory which was under the Mughals in Ujjain Sarkar of Malwa Kingdom.

The inscription establishes the antiquity of Kampel by 817 A.H. Kamel is a large village situated between 22°.37'N and 76°.03'E 20 miles southeast of Indore. It had a headquarters of a **Mahal** in Ujjain Sarkar of Subah Malwa. The local tradition traces its origin to a local Raja about a 1000 years ago.³ The architectural remain near the mosque in the village, vouchsafe it as a settlement of the Parmar period.⁴

It is every likelyhood that the mosque was named after Zamzamshah Pir, in whose memory, Jam Gate at Jam Ghat stands. The Holkars first came to Kampel and had established their Court and Capital here. So is the case of the historical family of Jamidar, Bada Rawala⁵. It appears that from ancient times Kampel was an important place because of nearness of the Ghats on the Narmada. Therefore, it is mentioned as Kampil Ghat in History.

The inscription reveals that by 817 A.H. the authority of Musa Khan from Narmada region was terminated and Alp Khan's established instead.

2. For Comparative Study refer to, **Ain-i-Akbari**, Vol.II (Eng.Tr.Jarrett) p.209.
3. **Holkar State Gazetteer**, 1930, pp. 604-605.
4. For monuments refer plate on p.118.
5. **Holkar State Gazetteer**, p. 605
5. **Holkar State Gazetteer**, p.605.

The building in Kampel where inscription is fixed.

The Inscription of Hoshang Shah.

The architectural remains of Parmar period near the building.

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